

4 : 4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl-3 : 3'-dialdehyde (*Bis-salicylaldehyde*) and its Derivatives.

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4 : 4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl-3 : 3'-dialdehyde (I) has now been prepared for the first time by the application of Reimer and Tiemann's reaction to *pp'*-dihydroxydiphenyl (yield 50 per cent.) using chloroform mixed with alcohol (1:4). It is a yellow microcrystalline powder m.p. 185°, gives a dibenzoyl derivative and a diphenylhydrazone, a dioxime and a disemicarbazone. It also forms a bisulphite compound in alcoholic solution.

It undergoes the benzoin condensation in the usual manner producing compound (II) and also reacts with acetone in the presence of 40 per cent. sodium hydroxide solution. When heated with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, the dialdehyde produces 6 : 6'-dicoumaryl (III), identical with the compound prepared by Sen and Chakravarti from 6-iodocoumarin by heating with copper powder (*private communication*).

Bis-salicylaldehyde, like 6-aldehydocoumarin, aldehydophenolphthalein and aldehydofluorescein (Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2428; Sen and Kar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*,

1929, 6, 54; Sen and Banerjee, *ibid*, 1929, 6, 505), gives rise to various interesting dyes with multiple chromophores by its condensation with different aromatic amino- and hydroxy-compounds. Azomethine compounds have been obtained by condensing the aldehyde with mono- and di-amines: Two molecules of a monoamine and one molecule of a diamine ordinarily react with one molecule of the aldehyde, ring compounds being obtained with benzidine (IV) and with *o*- and *p*-phenylenediamines (V). In the case of *m*-phenylenediamine, however, two molecules of the amine condense with one molecule of the aldehyde, the presence of free amino-groups in the product (VI) being proved by diazotisation.

Pyronine dyes have been obtained by condensing a molecule of the aldehyde with four molecules of (a) diethyl-*m*-aminophenol, (b) resorcinol and (c) pyrogallol in the presence of sulphuric acid (*d* 1·84) in the manner described by Sen and Sinha (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 2984). The diethyl-*m*-aminophenol condensation product is soluble both in acids and alkalis and dyes wool and silk a violet shade; the pyrogallol compound gives an octapotassium salt and is polygenetic (brownish-black with iron mordant and olive-green with chromium mordant), while the resorcinol compound gives a tetrapotassium salt dyeing an orange shade, and an octabromo-derivative, which dyes wool and silk a beautiful red shade.

Triphenylmethane dyes have been obtained by condensing the aldehyde with (a) dimethylaniline and (b) *o*-cresotinic acid; the leuco-bases, on oxidation, give a fine bluish dye in the first case and a mordant dye (yellowish-red with aluminium mordant) in the second case.

Incidentally it may also be mentioned that by the application of Reimer and Tiemann's reaction with carbon tetrachloride on an alkaline solution of *pp'*-dihydroxydiphenyl, a dicarboxylic acid, identical with the acid prepared from *bis*-anthranilic acid (Bülow and Reden, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2577), has been obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Bis-salicylaldehyde (4 : 4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl-3 : 3'-dialdehyde).—To a solution of *pp'*-dihydroxydiphenyl (15 g.) in caustic soda solution (30 g. in 70 c.c. water) heated on a water-bath at 40-50°, and stirred with a mechanical stirrer a mixture of alcohol and chloroform (4 : 1; 25 c.c. chloroform in all) is added drop by drop and the solution kept at this temperature with continuous stirring for twelve hours. The excess of chloroform being distilled off, the solution is cooled, diluted with water and acidified with acetic acid. The precipitate is filtered off, washed with water and dried. It is extracted repeatedly with ether, in which the parent phenol is readily soluble while the aldehyde is quite insoluble. It is finally crystallised from a mixture of acetone and alcohol (6 : 1), in yellow microcrystalline powder melting at 185° (yield, 8 g.). It is readily soluble in acetone and pyridine, less so in alcohol and glacial acetic acid, insoluble in ether, chloroform, benzene, carbon disulphide and carbon tetrachloride. It dissolves in aqueous caustic alkalis and alkaline carbonates (red solution). (Found: C, 68.95, 69.24; H, 4.3, 4.13. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 69.42; H, 4.10 per cent.).

The *diphenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallises from dilute pyridine in yellow microcrystalline powder melting at 215°. It dissolves in caustic alkalis and sparingly in alkaline carbonates (yellowish-brown solution). (Found: N, 13.42; 13.5. $C_{26}H_{22}O_2N_4$ requires N, 13.27 per cent.).

The *disemicarbazone*, prepared as usual, is obtained from pyridine in the form of yellow powder; it does not melt up to 300°. (Found: N, 23.4, 23.7. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4N_6$ requires N, 23.6 per cent.).

The *dioxime*, prepared as usual, is obtained from absolute alcohol in the form of dark yellow powder which does not melt up to 300°. (Found: N, 10.47. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.3 per cent.).

The *dibenzoyl* derivative, prepared by Schotten-Bauman's method, crystallises from ethyl acetate as large feathery crystals melting at 100°. (Found: C, 74.4. H, 4.02. $C_{28}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 74.6; H, 4.00 per cent.).

Benzoin Condensation.—A solution of the aldehyde (3 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) with 1 per cent. aqueous alcoholic solution of potassium cyanide (10 c.c.) is heated on the water-bath (6 hours). The solution on acidification with hydrochloric acid, gives a yellow precipitate which is filtered off and washed with water. It is finally crystallised from alcohol in the form of reddish-brown microcrystal-

line powder, which does not melt up to 303° . It readily reduces Fehling's solution and dissolves in dilute caustic alkalis and alkaline carbonates. (Found: C, 69.49; H, 4.13. $C_{28}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 69.42; H, 4.13 per cent.).

Condensation with Acetone.—To a solution of the aldehyde (2 g.), acetone (10 c.c.) and caustic soda solution (40 per cent., 10 c.c.) are added and the solution left overnight; the solid, that separates, is filtered off and is obtained in the form of a deep red powder from glacial acetic acid, not melting up to 300° . (Found: C, 74.42, 74.23; H, 5.59, 5.58. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 74.53; H, 5.59 per cent.).

6:6'-Dicoumaryl.—The aldehyde (4 g.) is moistened with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) in a dry conical flask and fused sodium acetate (3 g.) is added and the mass is stirred with a glass rod with a few crystals of iodine. 1 C.c. of pyridine is added and the flask is then heated with an air condenser in an oil-bath at $120-30^{\circ}$ for 2 hours. The temperature is then raised to $190-200^{\circ}$ and maintained there for 8 hours. The mass is then cooled, washed with water and is extracted repeatedly with sodium carbonate solution which dissolved the unchanged aldehyde. It is then dissolved in caustic soda solution and carbon dioxide is passed through it which further precipitates the remaining quantity of the aldehyde. The process is repeated until no more precipitation takes place with carbon dioxide. The filtrate is then boiled to expel carbon dioxide and is acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when the coumarin compound is precipitated. It is dissolved in pyridine and is precipitated by pouring the solution into a large volume of water and is finally crystallised from dilute pyridine in the form of yellowish-brown powder which decomposes above 200° (yield 40 per cent.). The product is soluble in pyridine, less so in chloroform, acetone, methyl and ethyl alcohols. It is insoluble in carbon bisulphide, ether, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, petroleum, ether and water. (Found: C, 74.5, 74.3; H, 3.5, 3.4. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 74.4; H, 3.4 per cent.).

Azomethine Derivatives.

The general method of preparation of these compounds is to add an alcoholic solution of an amine to an alcoholic solution of the aldehyde; crystals often separate on mixing the hot solutions. The reaction is finished by heating the solution on the water-bath sometimes with the addition of a little fused sodium acetate. The

product is washed with dilute acids and crystallised. The yield is generally theoretical. The azomethine compounds are described in Table A.

Pyronine and Triphenylmethane Dyes.

The general method of preparation of these dyes is to treat the mixture of the aldehyde (1 mol.) and the hydroxy-compound (4 mols.) with concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84) sufficient to make the mixture a paste. The mixture is then heated at about $120\text{--}30^\circ$ for sometime, when sulphur dioxide escapes. The product is then isolated by pouring into water and purified by acid and alkali treatment. It is finally crystallised from a suitable solvent. The condensation with dimethylaniline is effected in the presence of hydrochloric acid. Compounds of these series are listed in Table B.

4 : 4'-Dihydroxydiphenyl-3 : 3'-dicarboxylic Acid.—The preparation of this compound is the same as that of the dialdehyde but instead of chloroform carbon tetrachloride has been used. The crude product is purified by treatment with acetic acid in the cold in which the acid is readily soluble whilst the diphenol is very sparingly soluble. The solution is then poured into water, the precipitate is allowed to settle and filtered. It is finally crystallised from acetic acid in the form of yellow powder which melts slightly above 300° . The yield is 40 per cent.

TABLE A.
Azomethine Compounds.

Formulae.	Method of preparation (A = The aldehyde).	P.c. of N.		Appearance and melting point.	Remarks.
		Calc.	Found.		
$C_{26}H_{20}O_2N_2$	A + aniline + sodium acetate.	7.1	7.3 6.96	Reddish-brown powder, not melting up to 300°.	Crystallises from amyl alcohol. Soluble in alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate and acetic acid.
$C_{28}H_{24}O_2N_2$	A + <i>p</i> -toluidine + sodium acetate.	6.6	6.3 6.9	Small red needles softening at 175°.	Crystallises from pyridine. Sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone.
$C_{38}H_{28}O_2N_6$	A + aminoazobenzene.	14	14.3 13.9	Red microcrystalline powder, m.p. 260°.	Crystallises from pyridine; Sparingly soluble in acetic acid, alcohol and acetone.
$C_{36}H_{18}O_2N_2$	A (1 mol.) + benzidine (1 mol.).	7.2	6.95 6.89	Reddish-brown powder not melting up to 300°.	Crystallises from aniline; soluble in pyridine and insoluble in alcohol and acetone.
$C_{20}H_{14}O_2N_2$	A (1 mol.) + <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine (1 mol.).	8.9	8.5 8.7	„	Crystallises from aniline, soluble in pyridine and insoluble in benzene, nitrobenzene, alcohol and acetone.
$C_{20}H_{14}O_2N_2$	A (1 mol.) + <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine (1 mol.).	8.9	8.63	Dark red powder, not melting up to 300°.	Crystallises from aniline, soluble in pyridine and aniline.
$C_{26}H_{22}O_2N_4$	A (1 mol.) + <i>m</i> -phenylenediamine (2 mols.).	13.3	13.4	Does not melt up to 300°.	Soluble in aniline and pyridine; insoluble in nitrobenzene, alcohol and acetone. The presence of the free amino-groups is proved by diazotisation.

TABLE B.
Pyronine Dyes.

Formula.	Method of preparation (A = The aldehyde).	M. p.	Shade on wool and silk.	Analysis :		Remarks.
				Calc.	Found.	
$C_{54}H_{62}O_6N_4$	A(1 mol.) + diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol (4 mol.) + H_2SO_4 (<i>d</i> 1.84) at 120°-130°.	Does not melt up to 300°.	Violet	N, 6.5	N, 6.7 6.8	Violet powder from dilute alcohol, soluble in acids and in alkalis.
$C_{38}H_{22}O_8$	A(1 mol.) + resorcinol (4 mol.) + H_2SO_4 on the water-bath for 6 hrs.	„	Orange	C, 75.2 H, 3.63	C, 75.09 H, 3.66	Red microcrystalline powder from dilute alcohol, alkaline solution exhibiting a green fluorescence.
$C_{38}H_{18}O_4K_4$	Prepared in the usual manner.	—	—	K, 20.6	K, 20.2	Long red needles from water.
$C_{38}H_{14}O_8Br_8$	By adding bromine to a solution of the substance.	„	Brilliant red	Br, 51.6	Br, 51.2	Deep red microcrystalline powder.
$C_{38}H_{12}O_{12}$	A(1 mol.) + pyrogallol (4 mol.) + H_2SO_4 on the water-bath for 6 hrs.	„	Black (iron mordant), green (chromium mordant).	C, 68.06 H, 3.3	C, 68.2 H, 3.3	Greyish-black powder from alcohol.
$C_{38}H_{14}O_{12}K_8$...	—	—	K, 32.03	K, 32.2	—

Triphenylmethane Dyes.

$C_{46}H_{50}O_2N_4$	A(1 mol.) + dimethylaniline (4 mol.) + HCl on the water-bath for 30 hrs.	Does not melt up to 300°.	Bluish-green by the oxidised base.	N, 8.11	N, 8.3, 8.2	Star-shaped crystals from alcohol, oxidised with PbO_2 in the usual manner.
$C_{46}H_{38}O_{14}$	A(1 mol.) + <i>o</i> -cresotinic acid (4 mol.) + H_2SO_4 in the cold for 24 hrs.	Decomposed at 225°.	Yellowish-red (iron, aluminium and chromium mordant) by the oxidised base.	C, 67.8 H, 4.7	C, 67.61 H, 4.7	Brown powder by precipitation from the ethereal solution by benzene. Oxidised with nitrosyl sulphate.

